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---
title: "Thesis_study4_chapter8_ML_code"
author: "Hana Sediva"
date: "2024-08-05"
output:
  pdf_document: default
  html_document: default
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```

```
```${r setup, include=FALSE}
knitr::opts_chunk$set(echo = TRUE)
```
```

This file is used to conduct feature selection on the intervention data, using Random Forest algorithm. The analysis is using 22 time-varying features and 20 time-constant features with 10 outcomes to identify groups of predictors with the greatest impact on intervention outcomes.

```
```${r}
#load libraries
install.packages("tidyverse") # data management package
install.packages("dplyr") # data management package
install.packages("lme4") # multilevel package
install.packages("plm") # fixed effect package
install.packages("Hmisc") #correlation
install.packages("corrplot") #plotting
install.packages("caret") #feature selection ML package
install.packages("mlbench") # used for benchmarking
install.packages("ggcorrplot") #plotting
install.packages("randomForest") #ML algorithm
install.packages('broom') # for glance function()
```

```
library(ggcorrplot)
library("randomForest")
library(mlbench)
library("caret")
library(corrplot)
library("tidyverse")
library("dplyr")
library("lme4")
library("plm")
library("zoo")
library("Hmisc")
library("ggpubr")
library(broom)
```
```

Create a dataframe with 22 time-varying predictors and 10 outcomes

```
```${r}
dfStudy4_final_intervention <- subset(dfStudy4_final, wave >= 1 & wave <= 14)
dfPredictors <- subset(dfStudy4_final_intervention, select = c(
#time-varying predictors:
"ema_daily_total_surveys_answered",
"ema_daily_total_education_shown",
"ema_daily_total_education_read",
"ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary",
"ema_veg_portions_goal",
"ema_fruit_portions_goal",
"ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA",
"ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_binary",
"ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA",
"ema_lunch_colourful_rating_binary",
"ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA",
"ema_dinner_colourful_rating_binary",
"ema_had_alcohol_last_night",
"ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary",
"ema_group_exercise_participation_binary",
"ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary",
```

```
"ema_afternoon_exercise_plan_binary",
"ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary",
"ema_steps_goal_binary",
"ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA",
"ema_human_coach_interaction",
"ema_sleep_quality_transformed_scale",
```

```
#Outcome:
```

```
"daily_total_steps_scaled",
"daily_total_sleep_scaled",
"daily_deep_sleep_scaled",
"daily_total_veg",
"daily_total_fruit",
"daily_total_water",
"daily_total_caffeine",
"daily_total_alcohol",
"daily_total_snacks",
"daily_total_meals"
```

```
))
```
```

```
Create a dataframe with 20 time-constant predictors and 10 outcomes
```

```
```{r}
```

```
#constant predictors:
```

```
dfPredictors_constant <- subset(dfStudy4_final, select = c(
"survey_pre_age_group_fct",
"survey_pre_location_fct",
"survey_pre_tech_user_fct", #binary, asked at baseline
"survey_pre_health_status_fct", #scale, asked at baseline
"survey_pre_HRT_fct", #binary, never took or currently/in the past
"survey_pre_antidepressants_fct",
"survey_pre_CBT_fct",
"survey_pre_smoking_fct",
"survey_pre_generation_british_fct",
"ema_group_exercise_participation_fct",
"survey_pre_marital_status_fct",
"survey_pre_num_children_fct",
"survey_pre_children_home_fct",
"survey_pre_ethnicity_fct",
"survey_pre_qualification_fct",
"survey_pre_employment_fct",
"survey_pre_income_fct",
"survey_pre_meno_stage_fct",
"survey_pre_meno_perspective_fct",
"survey_pre_meno_knowledge_fct",
```

```
#Outcome:
```

```
"daily_total_steps_scaled",
"daily_total_sleep_scaled",
"daily_deep_sleep_scaled",
"daily_total_veg",
"daily_total_fruit",
"daily_total_water",
"daily_total_caffeine",
"daily_total_alcohol",
"daily_total_snacks",
"daily_total_meals"
```

```
))
```
```

```
Create correlation matrix and write to a file
```

```
```{r}
```

```
w = dfStudy4_final_intervention$response_weight
```

```

matStudy4 <- as.matrix(dfPredictors)

weighted_corr <- cov.wt(matStudy4, wt = w, cor = TRUE)
corr_matrix <- weighted_corr$cor

write.csv(corr_matrix,
 file = "C:/R_code/study4/Weighted_spearman_cor_matrix_Aug5.csv",
 row.names = FALSE)
...

**** Steps count outcome ****

Time-constant predictors:
Create an RFE model with 20 constant predictors for steps count outcome
```{r}
set.seed(7)
# load the library
library(mlbench)
library(caret)

# define the control using a random forest selection function
control <- rfeControl(functions=rfFuncs, method="cv", number=10)
# run the RFE algorithm. Use 20 time-constant predictors.
results <- rfe(dfPredictors_constant[, 1:20], dfPredictors_constant[[21]],
              sizes=c(1:20), rfeControl=control)
# summarize the results
print(results)
# list the chosen features
predictors(results)

# plot the results
plot(results, type=c("g", "o"))

#summary(results$results$RMSE.)
summary(results)

#display top 10 predictors
varimp_data <- data.frame(feature = row.names(varImp(results))[1:17],
                          importance = varImp(results)[1:17, 1])

#plot top 10 predictors
ggplot(data = varimp_data,
        aes(x = reorder(feature, importance), y = importance, fill = feature)) +
  geom_bar(stat="identity") + #labs(x = "Features", y = "Variable Importance") +
  geom_text(aes(label = round(importance, 2)), vjust=1.6, color="white", size=4) +
  theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") + coord_flip() +
  labs(y = "Variable Importance",
       x = "Features",
       color = "blue",
       linetype = "blue",
       title = "Top 17 time-constant predictors for steps count",
       subtitle = "Recursive feature elimination",
       caption = "Data: Intervention data including baseline (wave 0-14)")
...

Create a linear model with the selected subset of 17 time-constant predictors and
identify statistically significant predictors for steps count outcome.
```{r}
dfPredictors_0 <- data.frame(dfPredictors_constant[c(1:20,21)])

dfPredictors_1 <- select(dfPredictors_0, daily_total_steps_scaled,
 survey_pre_location_fct,
 survey_pre_meno_perspective_fct,
 survey_pre_ethnicity_fct,
 survey_pre_meno_stage_fct,

```

```

 survey_pre_CBT_fct,
 ema_group_exercise_participation_fct,
 survey_pre_income_fct,
 survey_pre_meno_knowledge_fct,
 survey_pre_age_group_fct,
 survey_pre_health_status_fct,
 survey_pre_HRT_fct,
 survey_pre_antidepressants_fct,
 survey_pre_generation_british_fct,
 survey_pre_num_children_fct,
 survey_pre_smoking_fct,
 survey_pre_marital_status_fct,
 survey_pre_qualification_fct
)
model_constant1 <- lm(daily_total_steps_scaled ~., data = dfPredictors_1)

summary(model_constant1)

glance(model_constant1) %>%
 dplyr::select(r.squared, adj.r.squared, sigma, statistic, AIC, BIC, p.value)
...

```

#### Time-varying predictors:

Create an RFE model with 22 time-varying predictors for steps count outcome

```

```{r}
set.seed(7)
# load the library
library(mlbench)
library(caret)

# define the control using a random forest selection function
control <- rfeControl(functions=rffuncs, method="cv", number=10)
# run the RFE algorithm
results <- rfe(dfPredictors[, 1:22], dfPredictors[[23]], sizes=c(1:22),
rfeControl=control)
# summarize the results
print(results)
# list the chosen features
predictors(results)

# plot the results
plot(results, type=c("g", "o"))

#display top 10 predictors
varimp_data <- data.frame(feature = row.names(varImp(results))[1:6],
importance = varImp(results)[1:6, 1])

#plot top 10 predictors
ggplot(data = varimp_data,
aes(x = reorder(feature, importance), y = importance, fill = feature)) +
geom_bar(stat="identity") + #labs(x = "Features", y = "Variable Importance") +
geom_text(aes(label = round(importance, 2)), vjust=1.6, color="white", size=4) +
theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") + coord_flip() +
labs(y = "Variable Importance",
x = "Features",
color = "blue",
linetype = "blue",
title = "Top 6 time-varying predictors for steps count",
subtitle = "Recursive feature elimination",
caption = "Data: Intervention data excluding baseline (wave 1-14)")
...

```

Create a linear model with 6 time-varying predictors and identifying those that are statistically significant in predicting steps count outcome.

```

```{r}
dfPredictors_0 <- data.frame(dfPredictors[c(1:22,23)])
dfPredictors_1 <- select(dfPredictors_0, daily_total_steps_scaled,

```

```

 ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary,
 ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA,
 ema_veg_portions_goal,
 ema_group_exercise_participation_binary,
 ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary,
 ema_steps_goal_binary
)

modell1 <- lm(daily_total_steps_scaled ~., data = dfPredictors_1)

summary(modell1)
glance(modell1) %>%
 dplyr::select(r.squared, adj.r.squared, sigma, AIC, BIC, p.value)
...

***** Vegetables consumption outcome *****

Time-constant predictors:
Create an RFE model with 20 constant predictors for vegetables consumption outcome
```{r}
set.seed(7)
# load the library
library(mlbench)
library(caret)

# define the control using a random forest selection function
control <- rfeControl(functions=rfFuncs, method="cv", number=10)
# run the RFE algorithm. Use 20 time-constant predictors.
results <- rfe(dfPredictors_constant[, 1:20], dfPredictors_constant[[24]],
  sizes=c(1:20), rfeControl=control)
# summarize the results
print(results)
# list the chosen features
predictors(results)
# plot the results
plot(results, type=c("g", "o"))

#display top 10 predictors
varimp_data <- data.frame(feature = row.names(varImp(results))[1:8],
  importance = varImp(results)[1:8, 1])

#plot top 10 predictors
ggplot(data = varimp_data,
  aes(x = reorder(feature, importance), y = importance, fill = feature)) +
  geom_bar(stat="identity") + #labs(x = "Features", y = "Variable Importance") +
  geom_text(aes(label = round(importance, 2)), vjust=1.6, color="white", size=4) +
  theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") + coord_flip() +
  labs(y = "Variable Importance",
    x = "Features",
    color = "blue",
    linetype = "blue",
    title = "Top 8 time-constant predictors for daily vegetables portions",
    subtitle = "Recursive feature elimination",
    caption = "Data: Intervention data including baseline (wave 0-14)")
...

Create a linear model with the selected subset of 8 time-constant predictors and
identify statistically significant predictors for veg consumption outcome.
```{r}
dfPredictors_0 <- data.frame(dfPredictors_constant[c(1:20,24)])
dfPredictors_1 <- select(dfPredictors_0, daily_total_veg,
 survey_pre_ethnicity_fct,
 survey_pre_meno_perspective_fct,
 survey_pre_meno_stage_fct,
 ema_group_exercise_participation_fct,
 survey_pre_meno_knowledge_fct,
 survey_pre_location_fct,
 survey_pre_generation_british_fct,
 survey_pre_num_children_fct

```

```

)
model_constant_1 <- lm(daily_total_veg ~., data = dfPredictors_1)
summary(model_constant_1)

glance(model_constant_1) %>%
 dplyr::select(r.squared, adj.r.squared, sigma, AIC, BIC, p.value)
...

Time-varying predictors:
Create an RFE model with 22 time-varying predictors for veg consumption outcome
```{r}
set.seed(7)
# load the library
library(mlbench)
library(caret)

# define the control using a random forest selection function
control <- rfeControl(functions=rfFuncs, method="cv", number=10)
# run the RFE algorithm
results <- rfe(dfPredictors[, 1:22], dfPredictors[[26]], sizes=c(1:22),
rfeControl=control)
# summarize the results
print(results)
# list the chosen features
predictors(results)
# plot the results
plot(results, type=c("g", "o"))

#display top 10 predictors
varimp_data <- data.frame(feature = row.names(varImp(results))[1:10],
importance = varImp(results)[1:10, 1])

#plot top 10 predictors
ggplot(data = varimp_data,
aes(x = reorder(feature, importance), y = importance, fill = feature)) +
geom_bar(stat="identity") + #labs(x = "Features", y = "Variable Importance") +
geom_text(aes(label = round(importance, 2)), vjust=1.6, color="white", size=4) +
theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") + coord_flip() +
labs(y = "Variable Importance",
x = "Features",
color = "blue",
linetype = "blue",
title = "Top 10 time-varying predictors for daily vegetable portions",
subtitle = "Recursive feature elimination",
caption = "Data: Intervention data excluding baseline (wave 0-14)")
...

Create a linear model with 10 time-varying predictors and identifying those that are
statistically significant in predicting veg consumption outcome.
```{r}
dfPredictors_0 <- data.frame(dfPredictors[c(1:22,26)])
dfPredictors_1 <- select(dfPredictors_0, daily_total_veg,
ema_veg_portions_goal,
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA,
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA,
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA,
ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary,
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_binary,
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_binary,
ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA,
ema_daily_total_education_shown,
ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary
)
modell <- lm(daily_total_veg ~., data = dfPredictors_1)
summary(modell)
glance(modell) %>%
 dplyr::select(r.squared, adj.r.squared, sigma, AIC, BIC, p.value)
...

```

```
***** Fruit consumption outcome *****
```

```
Time-constant predictors:
```

```
Create an RFE model with 20 constant predictors for fruit consumption outcome
```

```
```{r}
set.seed(7)
# load the library
library(mlbench)
library(caret)

# define the control using a random forest selection function
control <- rfeControl(functions=rffuncs, method="cv", number=10)
# run the RFE algorithm. Use 20 time-constant predictors.
results <- rfe(dfPredictors_constant[, 1:20], dfPredictors_constant[[25]],
              sizes=c(1:20), rfeControl=control)
# summarize the results
print(results)
# list the chosen features
predictors(results)
# plot the results
plot(results, type=c("g", "o"))

#display top 10 predictors
varimp_data <- data.frame(feature = row.names(varImp(results))[1:4],
                          importance = varImp(results)[1:4, 1])

#plot top 10 predictors
ggplot(data = varimp_data,
        aes(x = reorder(feature, importance), y = importance, fill = feature)) +
  geom_bar(stat="identity") + #labs(x = "Features", y = "Variable Importance") +
  geom_text(aes(label = round(importance, 2)), vjust=1.6, color="white", size=4) +
  theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") + coord_flip() +
  labs(y = "Variable Importance",
       x = "Features",
       color = "blue",
       linetype = "blue",
       title = "Top 4 time-constant predictors for daily fruit portions",
       subtitle = "Recursive feature elimination",
       caption = "Data: Intervention data including baseline (wave 0-14)")
...

```

```
Create a linear model with the selected subset of 4 time-constant predictors and
identify statistically significant predictors for fruit consumption outcome.
```

```
```{r}
dfPredictors_0 <- data.frame(dfPredictors_constant[c(1:20,25)])
dfPredictors_1 <- select(dfPredictors_0, daily_total_fruit,
 survey_pre_location_fct,
 survey_pre_marital_status_fct,
 ema_group_exercise_participation_fct,
 survey_pre_age_group_fct
)

model_constant_1 <- lm(daily_total_fruit ~., data = dfPredictors_1)
summary(model_constant_1)

glance(model_constant_1) %>%
 dplyr::select(r.squared, adj.r.squared, sigma, AIC, BIC, p.value)
...

```

```
Time-varying predictors:
```

```
Create an RFE model with 22 time-varying predictors for fruit consumption outcome
```

```
```{r}
set.seed(7)
# load the library
library(mlbench)
library(caret)

# define the control using a random forest selection function

```

```

control <- rfeControl(functions=rfFuncs, method="cv", number=10)
# run the RFE algorithm
results <- rfe(dfPredictors[, 1:22], dfPredictors[[27]], sizes=c(1:22),
rfeControl=control)
# summarize the results
print(results)
# list the chosen features
predictors(results)
# plot the results
plot(results, type=c("g", "o"))

#display top 10 predictors
varimp_data <- data.frame(feature = row.names(varImp(results))[1:16],
importance = varImp(results)[1:16, 1])

#plot top 10 predictors
ggplot(data = varimp_data,
aes(x = reorder(feature, importance), y = importance, fill = feature)) +
geom_bar(stat="identity") + #labs(x = "Features", y = "Variable Importance") +
geom_text(aes(label = round(importance, 2)), vjust=1.6, color="white", size=4) +
theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") + coord_flip() +
labs(y = "Variable Importance",
x = "Features",
color = "blue",
linetype = "blue",
title = "Top 16 time-varying predictors for daily fruit portions",
subtitle = "Recursive feature elimination",
caption = "Data: Intervention data excluding baseline (wave 1-14)")
...

```

Create a linear model with xxxx time-varying predictors and identifying those that are statistically significant in predicting fruit consumption outcome.

```

```{r}
dfPredictors_0 <- data.frame(dfPredictors[c(1:22,27)])

dfPredictors_1 <- select(dfPredictors_0, daily_total_fruit,
ema_fruit_portions_goal,
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_binary,
ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA,
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_binary,
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA,
ema_daily_total_education_shown,
ema_veg_portions_goal,
ema_daily_total_education_read,
ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary,
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA,
ema_daily_total_surveys_answered,
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_binary,
ema_steps_goal_binary,
ema_group_exercise_participation_binary,
ema_had_alcohol_last_night,
ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary

)
modell1 <- lm(daily_total_fruit ~., data = dfPredictors_1)
summary(modell1)
glance(modell1) %>%
dplyr::select(r.squared, adj.r.squared, sigma, AIC, BIC, p.value)
...

```

\*\*\*\*\* Water intake (hydration) outcome \*\*\*\*\*

```

Time-constant predictors:
Create an RFE model with 20 constant predictors for water intake outcome
```{r}
set.seed(7)
# load the library
library(mlbench)
library(caret)

```

```

# define the control using a random forest selection function
control <- rfeControl(functions=rfFuncs, method="cv", number=10)
# run the RFE algorithm. Use 20 time-constant predictors.
results <- rfe(dfPredictors_constant[, 1:20], dfPredictors_constant[[26]],
sizes=c(1:20), rfeControl=control)
# summarize the results
print(results)
# list the chosen features
predictors(results)
# plot the results
plot(results, type=c("g", "o"))

#display top 10 predictors
varimp_data <- data.frame(feature = row.names(varImp(results))[1:4],
importance = varImp(results)[1:4, 1])

#plot top 10 predictors
ggplot(data = varimp_data,
aes(x = reorder(feature, importance), y = importance, fill = feature)) +
geom_bar(stat="identity") + #labs(x = "Features", y = "Variable Importance") +
geom_text(aes(label = round(importance, 2)), vjust=1.6, color="white", size=4) +
theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") + coord_flip() +
labs(y = "Variable Importance",
x = "Features",
color = "blue",
linetype = "blue",
title = "Top 4 time-constant predictors for glasses of water",
subtitle = "Recursive feature elimination",
caption = "Data: Intervention data including baseline (wave 0-14)")
...

```

Create a linear model with the selected subset of 4 time-constant predictors and identify statistically significant predictors for water intake outcome.

```

```{r}
dfPredictors_0 <- data.frame(dfPredictors_constant[c(1:20,26)])
dfPredictors_1 <- select(dfPredictors_0, daily_total_water,
survey_pre_location_fct,
survey_pre_meno_perspective_fct,
survey_pre_meno_stage_fct,
ema_group_exercise_participation_fct
)
model_constant_1 <- lm(daily_total_water ~., data = dfPredictors_1)
summary(model_constant_1)

glance(model_constant_1) %>%
dplyr::select(r.squared, adj.r.squared, sigma, AIC, BIC, p.value)
...

```

Time-varying predictors:

Create an RFE model with 22 time-varying predictors for water intake outcome

```

```{r}
set.seed(7)
# load the library
library(mlbench)
library(caret)

# define the control using a random forest selection function
control <- rfeControl(functions=rfFuncs, method="cv", number=10)
# run the RFE algorithm
results <- rfe(dfPredictors[, 1:22], dfPredictors[[28]], sizes=c(1:22),
rfeControl=control)
# summarize the results
print(results)
# list the chosen features
predictors(results)
# plot the results
plot(results, type=c("g", "o"))

#display top 10 predictors

```

```

varimp_data <- data.frame(feature = row.names(varImp(results))[1:17],
                          importance = varImp(results)[1:17, 1])
#plot top 10 predictors
ggplot(data = varimp_data,
       aes(x = reorder(feature, importance), y = importance, fill = feature)) +
  geom_bar(stat="identity") + #labs(x = "Features", y = "Variable Importance") +
  geom_text(aes(label = round(importance, 2)), vjust=1.6, color="white", size=4) +
  theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") + coord_flip() +
  labs(y = "Variable Importance",
       x = "Features",
       color = "blue",
       linetype = "blue",
       title = "Top 17 time-varying predictors for glasses of water",
       subtitle = "Recursive feature elimination",
       caption = "Data: Intervention data excluding baseline (wave 1-14)")
...

```

Create a linear model with 17 time-varying predictors and identifying those that are statistically significant in predicting water intake outcome.

```

```{r}
dfPredictors_0 <- data.frame(dfPredictors[c(1:22,28)])
dfPredictors_1 <- select(dfPredictors_0, daily_total_water,
 ema_veg_portions_goal,
 ema_fruit_portions_goal,
 ema_daily_total_education_shown,
 ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA,
 ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary,
 ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA,
 ema_had_alcohol_last_night,
 ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary,
 ema_group_exercise_participation_binary,
 ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary,
 ema_lunch_colourful_rating_binary,
 ema_daily_total_surveys_answered,
 ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA,
 ema_daily_total_education_read,
 ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary,
 ema_steps_goal_binary,
 ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA

)
modell1 <- lm(daily_total_water ~., data = dfPredictors_1)
summary(modell1)
glance(modell1) %>%
 dplyr::select(r.squared, adj.r.squared, sigma, AIC, BIC, p.value)
...

```

\*\*\*\*\* Alcohol consumption outcome \*\*\*\*\*

Time-constant predictors:

Create an RFE model with 20 constant predictors for alcohol consumption outcome

```

```{r}
set.seed(7)
# load the library
library(mlbench)
library(caret)

# define the control using a random forest selection function
control <- rfeControl(functions=rffuncs, method="cv", number=10)
# run the RFE algorithm. Use 20 time-constant predictors.
results <- rfe(dfPredictors_constant[, 1:20], dfPredictors_constant[[28]],
              sizes=c(1:20), rfeControl=control)
# summarize the results
print(results)
# list the chosen features
predictors(results)
# plot the results

```

```

plot(results, type=c("g", "o"))

#display top 10 predictors
varimp_data <- data.frame(feature = row.names(varImp(results))[1:5],
                          importance = varImp(results)[1:5, 1])

#plot top 10 predictors
ggplot(data = varimp_data,
       aes(x = reorder(feature, importance), y = importance, fill = feature)) +
  geom_bar(stat="identity") + #labs(x = "Features", y = "Variable Importance") +
  geom_text(aes(label = round(importance, 2)), vjust=1.6, color="white", size=4) +
  theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") + coord_flip() +
  labs(y = "Variable Importance",
       x = "Features",
       color = "blue",
       linetype = "blue",
       title = "Top 5 time-constant predictors for daily units of alcoholic beverages",
       subtitle = "Recursive feature elimination",
       caption = "Data: Intervention data including baseline (wave 0-14)")

...

Create a linear model with the selected subset of 5 time-constant predictors and
identify statistically significant predictors for alcohol consumption outcome.
```{r}
dfPredictors_0 <- data.frame(dfPredictors_constant[c(1:20,28)])
dfPredictors_1 <- select(dfPredictors_0, daily_total_alcohol,
 survey_pre_location_fct,
 survey_pre_antidepressants_fct,
 survey_pre_ethnicity_fct,
 survey_pre_HRT_fct,
 survey_pre_age_group_fct
)

model_constant_1 <- lm(daily_total_alcohol ~., data = dfPredictors_1)
summary(model_constant_1)

glance(model_constant_1) %>%
 dplyr::select(r.squared, adj.r.squared, sigma, AIC, BIC, p.value)

...

Time-varying predictors:
Create an RFE model with 22 time-varying predictors for alcohol consumption outcome
```{r}
set.seed(7)
# load the library
library(mlbench)
library(caret)

# define the control using a random forest selection function
control <- rfeControl(functions=rfFuncs, method="cv", number=10)
# run the RFE algorithm
results <- rfe(dfPredictors[, 1:22], dfPredictors[[30]], sizes=c(1:22),
              rfeControl=control)
# summarize the results
print(results)
# list the chosen features
predictors(results)
# plot the results
plot(results, type=c("g", "o"))

#display top 10 predictors
varimp_data <- data.frame(feature = row.names(varImp(results))[1:21],
                          importance = varImp(results)[1:21, 1])

#plot top 10 predictors
ggplot(data = varimp_data,
       aes(x = reorder(feature, importance), y = importance, fill = feature)) +
  geom_bar(stat="identity") + #labs(x = "Features", y = "Variable Importance") +
  geom_text(aes(label = round(importance, 2)), vjust=1.6, color="white", size=4) +

```

```

theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") + coord_flip() +
labs(y = "Variable Importance",
     x = "Features",
     color = "blue",
     linetype = "blue",
     title = "Top 21 time-varying predictors for daily units of alcohol",
     subtitle = "Recursive feature elimination",
     caption = "Data: Intervention data excluding baseline (wve 1-14)")

```

...

Create a linear model with 21 time-varying predictors and identifying those that are statistically significant in predicting alcohol consumption outcome.

```

```{r}
dfPredictors_0 <- data.frame(dfPredictors[c(1:22,30)])

dfPredictors_1 <- select(dfPredictors_0, daily_total_alcohol,
 ema_had_alcohol_last_night,
 ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA,
 ema_veg_portions_goal,
 ema_daily_total_education_read,
 ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary,
 ema_daily_total_education_shown,
 ema_group_exercise_participation_binary,
 ema_fruit_portions_goal,
 ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA,
 ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA,
 ema_lunch_colourful_rating_binary,
 ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary,
 ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary,
 ema_steps_goal_binary,
 ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary,
 ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_binary,
 ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA,
 ema_daily_total_surveys_answered,
 ema_human_coach_interaction,
 ema_dinner_colourful_rating_binary,
 ema_afternoon_exercise_plan_binary

)

modell <- lm(daily_total_alcohol ~., data = dfPredictors_1)
summary(modell)
glance(modell) %>%
 dplyr::select(r.squared, adj.r.squared, sigma, AIC, BIC, p.value)
```

```

***** Caffeine consumption outcome *****

Time-constant predictors:

Create an RFE model with 20 constant predictors for caffeine consumption outcome

```

```{r}
set.seed(7)
load the library
library(mlbench)
library(caret)

define the control using a random forest selection function
control <- rfeControl(functions=rfFuncs, method="cv", number=10)
run the RFE algorithm. Use 20 time-constant predictors.
results <- rfe(dfPredictors_constant[, 1:20], dfPredictors_constant[[27]],
 sizes=c(1:20), rfeControl=control)
summarize the results
print(results)
list the chosen features
predictors(results)
plot the results
plot(results, type=c("g", "o"))

```

```

#display top 10 predictors
varimp_data <- data.frame(feature = row.names(varImp(results))[1:5],
 importance = varImp(results)[1:5, 1])
#plot top 10 predictors
ggplot(data = varimp_data,
 aes(x = reorder(feature, importance), y = importance, fill = feature)) +
 geom_bar(stat="identity") + #labs(x = "Features", y = "Variable Importance") +
 geom_text(aes(label = round(importance, 2)), vjust=1.6, color="white", size=4) +
 theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") + coord_flip() +
 labs(y = "Variable Importance",
 x = "Features",
 color = "blue",
 linetype = "blue",
 title = "Top 5 time-constant predictors for daily cups of coffee",
 subtitle = "Recursive feature elimination",
 caption = "Data: Intervention data including baseline (wave 0-14)")

```

...

Create a linear model with the selected subset of 5 time-constant predictors and identify statistically significant predictors for caffeine consumption outcome.

```

```{r}
dfPredictors_0 <- data.frame(dfPredictors_constant[c(1:20,27)])
dfPredictors_1 <- select(dfPredictors_0, daily_total_caffeine,
                       survey_pre_location_fct,
                       survey_pre_meno_stage_fct,
                       survey_pre_meno_perspective_fct,
                       survey_pre_health_status_fct,
                       survey_pre_ethnicity_fct
                       )
model_constant_1 <- lm(daily_total_caffeine ~., data = dfPredictors_1)
summary(model_constant_1)

glance(model_constant_1) %>%
  dplyr::select(r.squared, adj.r.squared, sigma, AIC, BIC, p.value)

```

...

Time-varying predictors:

Create an RFE model with 22 time-varying predictors for caffeine consumption outcome

```

```{r}
set.seed(7)
load the library
library(mlbench)
library(caret)

define the control using a random forest selection function
control <- rfeControl(functions=rfFuncs, method="cv", number=10)
run the RFE algorithm
results <- rfe(dfPredictors[, 1:22], dfPredictors[[29]], sizes=c(1:22),
 rfeControl=control)
summarize the results
print(results)
list the chosen features
predictors(results)
plot the results
plot(results, type=c("g", "o"))

#display top 10 predictors
varimp_data <- data.frame(feature = row.names(varImp(results))[1:10],
 importance = varImp(results)[1:10, 1])
#plot top 10 predictors
ggplot(data = varimp_data,
 aes(x = reorder(feature, importance), y = importance, fill = feature)) +
 geom_bar(stat="identity") + #labs(x = "Features", y = "Variable Importance") +
 geom_text(aes(label = round(importance, 2)), vjust=1.6, color="white", size=4) +
 theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") + coord_flip() +
 labs(y = "Variable Importance",
 x = "Features",

```

```

color = "blue",
linetype = "blue",
title = "Top 10 time-varying predictors for daily cups of coffee",
subtitle = "Recursive feature elimination",
caption = "Data: Intervention data excluding baseline (wave 1-14)"

```

```

...

```

Create a linear model with 10 time-varying predictors and identifying those that are statistically significant in predicting caffeine consumption outcome.

```

```{r}
dfPredictors_0 <- data.frame(dfPredictors[c(1:22,29)])

dfPredictors_1 <- select(dfPredictors_0, daily_total_caffeine,
  ema_daily_total_education_shown,
  ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA,
  ema_veg_portions_goal,
  ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA,
  ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA,
  ema_daily_total_surveys_answered,
  ema_lunch_colourful_rating_binary,
  ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary,
  ema_had_alcohol_last_night,
  ema_fruit_portions_goal
)

modell1 <- lm(daily_total_caffeine ~., data = dfPredictors_1)
summary(modell1)
glance(modell1) %>%
  dplyr::select(r.squared, adj.r.squared, sigma, AIC, BIC, p.value)

```

```

...

```

***** Snacks consumption outcome *****

Time-constant predictors:

Create an RFE model with 20 constant predictors for snacks consumption outcome

```

```{r}
set.seed(7)
load the library
library(mlbench)
library(caret)

define the control using a random forest selection function
control <- rfeControl(functions=rfFuncs, method="cv", number=10)
run the RFE algorithm. Use 20 time-constant predictors.
results <- rfe(dfPredictors_constant[, 1:20], dfPredictors_constant[[29]],
 sizes=c(1:20), rfeControl=control)
summarize the results
print(results)
list the chosen features
predictors(results)
plot the results
plot(results, type=c("g", "o"))

#display top 10 predictors
varimp_data <- data.frame(feature = row.names(varImp(results))[1:5],
 importance = varImp(results)[1:5, 1])

#plot top 10 predictors
ggplot(data = varimp_data,
 aes(x = reorder(feature, importance), y = importance, fill = feature)) +
 geom_bar(stat="identity") +
 geom_text(aes(label = round(importance, 2)), vjust=1.6, color="white", size=4) +
 theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") + coord_flip() +
 labs(y = "Variable Importance",
 x = "Features",
 color = "blue",
 linetype = "blue",
 title = "Top 5 time-constant predictors for daily snacks portions",

```

```
 subtitle = "Recursive feature elimination",
 caption = "Data: Intervention data including baseline (wave 0-14)"
...

```

Create a linear model with the selected subset of 5 time-constant predictors and identify statistically significant predictors for snacks consumption outcome.

```
```{r}
dfPredictors_0 <- data.frame(dfPredictors_constant[c(1:20,29)])
dfPredictors_1 <- select(dfPredictors_0, daily_total_snacks,
  survey_pre_income_fct,
  survey_pre_marital_status_fct,
  survey_pre_location_fct,
  survey_pre_ethnicity_fct,
  survey_pre_health_status_fct
)
model_constant_1 <- lm(daily_total_snacks ~., data = dfPredictors_1)
summary(model_constant_1)

glance(model_constant_1) %>%
  dplyr::select(r.squared, adj.r.squared, sigma, AIC, BIC, p.value)
...

```

Time-varying predictors:

Create an RFE model with 22 time-varying predictors for snacks consumption outcome

```
```{r}
set.seed(7)
load the library
library(mlbench)
library(caret)

define the control using a random forest selection function
control <- rfeControl(functions=rffuncs, method="cv", number=10)
run the RFE algorithm
results <- rfe(dfPredictors[, 1:22], dfPredictors[[31]], sizes=c(1:22),
rfeControl=control)
summarize the results
print(results)
list the chosen features
predictors(results)
plot the results
plot(results, type=c("g", "o"))

#display top 10 predictors
varimp_data <- data.frame(feature = row.names(varImp(results))[1:18],
 importance = varImp(results)[1:18, 1])

#plot top 10 predictors
ggplot(data = varimp_data,
 aes(x = reorder(feature, importance), y = importance, fill = feature)) +
 geom_bar(stat="identity") + #labs(x = "Features", y = "Variable Importance") +
 geom_text(aes(label = round(importance, 2)), vjust=1.6, color="white", size=4) +
 theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") + coord_flip() +
 labs(y = "Variable Importance",
 x = "Features",
 color = "blue",
 linetype = "blue",
 title = "Top 18 time-varying predictors for daily snack portions",
 subtitle = "Recursive feature elimination",
 caption = "Data: Intervention data excluding baseline (wave 1-14)")
...

```

Create a linear model with 18 time-varying predictors and identifying those that are statistically significant in predicting snacks consumption outcome.

```
```{r}
dfPredictors_0 <- data.frame(dfPredictors[c(1:22,31)])

dfPredictors_1 <- select(dfPredictors_0, daily_total_snacks,

```

```

        ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA,
        ema_veg_portions_goal,
        ema_had_alcohol_last_night,
        ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA,
        ema_group_exercise_participation_binary,
        ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_binary,
        ema_fruit_portions_goal,
        ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary,
        ema_sleep_quality_transformed_scale,
        ema_daily_total_surveys_answered,
        ema_daily_total_education_read,
        ema_steps_goal_binary,
        ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA,
        ema_daily_total_education_shown,
        ema_afternoon_exercise_plan_binary,
        ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary,
        ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary

    )
modell1 <- lm(daily_total_snacks ~., data = dfPredictors_1)
summary(modell1)
glance(modell1) %>%
  dplyr::select(r.squared, adj.r.squared, sigma, AIC, BIC, p.value)
...

***** Meals consumption outcome *****

Time-constant predictors:
Create an RFE model with 20 constant predictors for meals consumption outcome
```{r}
set.seed(7)
load the library
library(mlbench)
library(caret)

define the control using a random forest selection function
control <- rfeControl(functions=rffuncs, method="cv", number=10)
run the RFE algorithm. Use 20 time-constant predictors.
results <- rfe(dfPredictors_constant[, 1:20], dfPredictors_constant[[30]],
 sizes=c(1:20), rfeControl=control)
summarize the results
print(results)
list the chosen features
predictors(results)
plot the results
plot(results, type=c("g", "o"))

#display top 10 predictors
varimp_data <- data.frame(feature = row.names(varImp(results))[1:8],
 importance = varImp(results)[1:8, 1])
#plot top 10 predictors
ggplot(data = varimp_data,
 aes(x = reorder(feature, importance), y = importance, fill = feature)) +
 geom_bar(stat="identity") + #labs(x = "Features", y = "Variable Importance") +
 geom_text(aes(label = round(importance, 2)), vjust=1.6, color="white", size=4) +
 theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") + coord_flip() +
 labs(y = "Variable Importance",
 x = "Features",
 color = "blue",
 linetype = "blue",
 title = "Top 8 time-constant predictors for daily number of meals",
 subtitle = "Recursive feature elimination",
 caption = "Data: Intervention data including baseline (wave 0-14)")
...

Create a linear model with the selected subset of 8 time-constant predictors and

```



```

 ema_lunch_colourful_rating_binary,
 ema_dinner_colourful_rating_binary,
 ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA,
 ema_group_exercise_participation_binary,
 ema_had_alcohol_last_night,
 ema_sleep_quality_transformed_scale,
 ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary,
 ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA,
 ema_steps_goal_binary,
 ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary,
 ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary,
 ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary,
 ema_veg_portions_goal,
 ema_daily_total_education_read,
 ema_afternoon_exercise_plan_binary

)
modell1 <- lm(daily_total_meals ~., data = dfPredictors_1)
summary(modell1)
glance(modell1) %>%
 dplyr::select(r.squared, adj.r.squared, sigma, AIC, BIC, p.value)
...

***** Total sleep minutes (quantity) outcome *****

Time-constant predictors:
Create an RFE model with 20 constant predictors for sleep quantity outcome
```{r}
set.seed(7)
# load the library
library(mlbench)
library(caret)

# define the control using a random forest selection function
control <- rfeControl(functions=rfFuncs, method="cv", number=10)
# run the RFE algorithm. Use 20 time-constant predictors.
results <- rfe(dfPredictors_constant[, 1:20], dfPredictors_constant[[22]],
  sizes=c(1:20), rfeControl=control)
# summarize the results
print(results)
# list the chosen features
predictors(results)
# plot the results
plot(results, type=c("g", "o"))

#display top 10 predictors
varimp_data <- data.frame(feature = row.names(varImp(results))[1:5],
  importance = varImp(results)[1:5, 1])
#plot top 10 predictors
ggplot(data = varimp_data,
  aes(x = reorder(feature, importance), y = importance, fill = feature)) +
  geom_bar(stat="identity") + #labs(x = "Features", y = "Variable Importance") +
  geom_text(aes(label = round(importance, 2)), vjust=1.6, color="white", size=4) +
  theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") + coord_flip() +
  labs(y = "Variable Importance",
    x = "Features",
    color = "blue",
    linetype = "blue",
    title = "Top 5 time-constant predictors for total sleep time",
    subtitle = "Recursive feature elimination",
    caption = "Data: Intervention data including baseline (wave 0-14)")
...

Create a linear model with the selected subset of 5 time-constant predictors and
identify statistically significant predictors for sleep quantity outcome.
```{r}
dfPredictors_0 <- data.frame(dfPredictors_constant[c(1:20,22)])

```

```

dfPredictors_1 <- select(dfPredictors_0, daily_total_sleep_scaled,
 survey_pre_ethnicity_fct,
 survey_pre_meno_perspective_fct,
 survey_pre_location_fct,
 survey_pre_employment_fct,
 survey_pre_income_fct
)
model_constant_1 <- lm(daily_total_sleep_scaled ~., data = dfPredictors_1)
summary(model_constant_1)

glance(model_constant_1) %>%
 dplyr::select(r.squared, adj.r.squared, sigma, AIC, BIC, p.value)
...

Time-varying predictors:
Create an RFE model with 22 time-varying predictors for sleep quantity outcome
```{r}
set.seed(7)
# load the library
library(mlbench)
library(caret)

# define the control using a random forest selection function
control <- rfeControl(functions=rfFuncs, method="cv", number=10)
# run the RFE algorithm
results <- rfe(dfPredictors[, 1:22], dfPredictors[[24]], sizes=c(1:22),
               rfeControl=control)
# summarize the results
print(results)
# list the chosen features
predictors(results)
# plot the results
plot(results, type=c("g", "o"))

#display top 10 predictors
varimp_data <- data.frame(feature = row.names(varImp(results))[1:6],
                          importance = varImp(results)[1:6, 1])
#plot top 10 predictors
ggplot(data = varimp_data,
        aes(x = reorder(feature, importance), y = importance, fill = feature)) +
  geom_bar(stat="identity") + #labs(x = "Features", y = "Variable Importance") +
  geom_text(aes(label = round(importance, 2)), vjust=1.6, color="white", size=4) +
  theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") + coord_flip() +
  labs(y = "Variable Importance",
        x = "Features",
        color = "blue",
        linetype = "blue",
        title = "Top 6 time-varying predictors for total sleep time",
        subtitle = "Recursive feature elimination",
        caption = "Data: Intervention data excluding baseline (wave 1-14)")
...

Create a linear model with 6 time-varying predictors and identifying those that are
statistically significant in predicting sleep quantity outcome.
```{r}
dfPredictors_0 <- data.frame(dfPredictors[c(1:22,24)])
dfPredictors_1 <- select(dfPredictors_0, daily_total_sleep_scaled,
 ema_daily_total_education_shown,
 ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA,
 ema_veg_portions_goal,
 ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA,
 ema_fruit_portions_goal,
 ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA
)
modell <- lm(daily_total_sleep_scaled ~., data = dfPredictors_1)
summary(modell)
glance(modell) %>%
 dplyr::select(r.squared, adj.r.squared, sigma, AIC, BIC, p.value)
...

```

```
***** Deep sleep minutes (quality) outcome *****
```

```
Time-constant predictors:
```

```
Create an RFE model with 20 constant predictors for sleep quality outcome
```

```
```{r}
```

```
set.seed(7)
```

```
# load the library
```

```
library(mlbench)
```

```
library(caret)
```

```
# define the control using a random forest selection function
```

```
control <- rfeControl(functions=rfFuncs, method="cv", number=10)
```

```
# run the RFE algorithm. Use 20 time-constant predictors.
```

```
results <- rfe(dfPredictors_constant[, 1:20], dfPredictors_constant[[23]],  
              sizes=c(1:20), rfeControl=control)
```

```
# summarize the results
```

```
print(results)
```

```
# list the chosen features
```

```
predictors(results)
```

```
# plot the results
```

```
plot(results, type=c("g", "o"))
```

```
#display top 10 predictors
```

```
varimp_data <- data.frame(feature = row.names(varImp(results))[1:2],  
                          importance = varImp(results)[1:2, 1])
```

```
#plot top 10 predictors
```

```
ggplot(data = varimp_data,
```

```
       aes(x = reorder(feature, importance), y = importance, fill = feature)) +
```

```
  geom_bar(stat="identity") + #labs(x = "Features", y = "Variable Importance") +
```

```
  geom_text(aes(label = round(importance, 2)), vjust=1.6, color="white", size=4) +
```

```
  theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") + coord_flip() +
```

```
  labs(y = "Variable Importance",
```

```
       x = "Features",
```

```
       color = "blue",
```

```
       linetype = "blue",
```

```
       title = "Top 2 time-constant predictors for deep sleep time",
```

```
       subtitle = "Recursive feature elimination",
```

```
       caption = "Data: Intervention data including baseline (wave 0-14)")
```

```
...
```

```
Create a linear model with the selected subset of 2 time-constant predictors and  
identify statistically significant predictors for sleep quality outcome.
```

```
```{r}
```

```
dfPredictors_0 <- data.frame(dfPredictors_constant[c(1:20,23)])
```

```
dfPredictors_1 <- select(dfPredictors_0, daily_deep_sleep_scaled,
 survey_pre_ethnicity_fct,
 survey_pre_location_fct
)
```

```
model_constant_1 <- lm(daily_deep_sleep_scaled ~., data = dfPredictors_1)
```

```
summary(model_constant_1)
```

```
glance(model_constant_1) %>%
```

```
 dplyr::select(r.squared, adj.r.squared, sigma, AIC, BIC, p.value)
```

```
...
```

```
Time-varying predictors:
```

```
Create an RFE model with 22 time-varying predictors for sleep quality outcome
```

```
```{r}
```

```
set.seed(7)
```

```
# load the library
```

```
library(mlbench)
```

```
library(caret)
```

```
# define the control using a random forest selection function
```

```
control <- rfeControl(functions=rfFuncs, method="cv", number=10)
```

```
# run the RFE algorithm
```

```
results <- rfe(dfPredictors[, 1:22], dfPredictors[[25]], sizes=c(1:22),
```

```

rfeControl=control)
# summarize the results
print(results)
# list the chosen features
predictors(results)
# plot the results
plot(results, type=c("g", "o"))

#display top 10 predictors
varimp_data <- data.frame(feature = row.names(varImp(results))[1:7],
                          importance = varImp(results)[1:7, 1])

#plot top 10 predictors
ggplot(data = varimp_data,
       aes(x = reorder(feature, importance), y = importance, fill = feature)) +
  geom_bar(stat="identity") + #labs(x = "Features", y = "Variable Importance") +
  geom_text(aes(label = round(importance, 2)), vjust=1.6, color="white", size=4) +
  theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") + coord_flip() +
  labs(y = "Variable Importance",
       x = "Features",
       color = "blue",
       linetype = "blue",
       title = "Top 7 time-varying predictors for deep sleep time",
       subtitle = "Recursive feature elimination",
       caption = "Data: Intervention data excluding baseline (wave 1-14)")
...

```

Create a linear model with 7 time-varying predictors and identifying those that are statistically significant in predicting sleep quality outcome.

```

```{r}
dfPredictors_0 <- data.frame(dfPredictors[c(1:22,25)])
dfPredictors_1 <- select(dfPredictors_0, daily_deep_sleep_scaled,
 ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA,
 ema_veg_portions_goal,
 ema_daily_total_education_shown,
 ema_afternoon_exercise_plan_binary,
 ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA,
 ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA,
 ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA
)

modell1 <- lm(daily_deep_sleep_scaled ~., data = dfPredictors_1)
summary(modell1)
glance(modell1) %>%
 dplyr::select(r.squared, adj.r.squared, sigma, AIC, BIC, p.value)
...

```